

Does Public Debt Crowd-Out Public Investment In East Africa Community?

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Abstract

Using an empirical model linking public debt to public investment, this study uses annual data from 1970-2010 and employs panel fixed-effects approach to estimate the effect of external and public debt, as a share of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), on public investment in East Africa Community (EAC). Levin-Lin-Chu test (LLC) and Engle-Granger approach were used to investigate the properties of the data with respect to Unit roots and Cointegration respectively. The Hausman specification test was used to select the panel fixed-effects model. The findings suggest that public debt negatively affects Public investments in EAC and that higher debt service crowds-out public sector spending.

Keywords: External Debt; Public Debt; Public Investment; Crowding-Out; Error Correction Model; East African Community

1. Introduction

Appropriate use of debt could lead to improved socio-economic growth and thus, better standards of living. In order to make debt effective, there is need for far reaching reforms in the management of the public sector. However in most cases, resources from debt have not been used as effectively, for example, projects financed by international loans have, due to lack of adequate or realistic planning, failed to generate sufficient resources to service the debt borrowed. Therefore, socio-economic development is compromised since the government spends huge sums on loan repayments, hence reducing money it spends on education, health and other social amenities, which mainly target the poor, who comprise the majority of the population (KENDREN, 2009).

According to Were (2001), three of the four key debt indicators in Kenya; debt-to-GNP ratio (50 per cent), debt to-exports ratio (275 per cent), debt service ratio (30 per cent) and interest-to-export ratio (20 per cent) have been above the critical levels (the numbers in brackets) since early 1980s. The debt service and the debt-to-GNP ratios have been above the critical levels since 1982, except in the late 1990s where the debt service ratio showed a slight decline. The debt-to- exports ratio has remained above the critical level from 1987 to 1994. These indicators show that the external debt problem began to rise faster in the early 1980s. The GDP growth rate remained below 5 per cent in the early 1980s. Although Kenya's debt burden indicators show a declining trend in the late 1990s, the huge transfers are alarming. The resources that could have been allocated to consumption and investment are instead being channelled abroad. This may act as a strong disincentive not only to invest but also to partake in any adjustment programmes aimed at increasing growth.

KENDREN (2009) argues that Kenya's public debt is dangerously high. Although the debt burden has contracted from 81 percent of the GDP in 1998 to 38.8 percent of GDP in 2008, it is still unsustainable. Kenya's declining economy cannot sustain the flow of repayment obligations arising out of a public debt of this magnitude. According to World Development Indicators (WDI) (2011), Kenya recorded a government debt to GDP of 57.33 percent in 2010, with internal and external debts being 29.96 percent and 27.33 percent respectively. With the current mode of spending coupled with the on-going operationalization of the new constitution that creates two levels of government, public expenditure will definitely rise and debt levels are likely to increase to astronomical levels hence questioning the government's borrowing prowess and control of the public purse.

A major external factor in Uganda's debt crisis is the dramatic decline in export receipts due to declining coffee prices and unfavorable terms of trade. The price of coffee (the major export) decreased steadily from 1985 to 1993 and Uganda suffered annual declines in its terms of trade every year from 1986 to 1992. The decline in the terms of trade resulted in a sharp increase in Uganda's debt service to exports ratio, which was over 60 percent between 1988 and 1993. Another major cause of debt was the high level of donor financed development expenditures. The reliance of the adjustment effort adopted in 1987 on external financing has created a larger debt burden for Uganda, with the external debt more than doubling during the adjustment period, moving from US\$1,659 million to \$2.9 billion as of June 1994. Most of this increase was attributable to credits obtained from multilateral institutions to support the balance of payments and finance development projects. Multilateral debt, as of June 1994, accounted for about 71 percent of the total debt stock, compared with about 43 percent in 1987 (Mbire and Atingi, 1997).

Heavily-indebted poor countries (HIPC) and Multilateral Debt Relief Initiative (MDRI) debt relief reduced Tanzania's debt burden sharply, with all debt indicators declining to levels well below risk thresholds. Debt policy has remained prudent since the provision of debt relief, with the total external debt declining from 57.3 percent of GDP in 2006 before MDRI went into effect, to 24.9 percent of GDP in 2008. Total external debt increased to 25.6 percent of GDP in 2009. Public domestic debt increased slightly from 13 percent of GDP in 2008 to 14.3 percent of GDP in 2009, about half of which was short term treasury bills (IMF and WB, 2010). Rwanda's external debt of the central government at the end of 2010 was 14.6 percent of GDP, including a small fraction which is guaranteed by the central government (0.4 percent of GDP). Multilateral creditors hold more than 80 percent of all central government external debt, with the lion share held by the IDA and ADB for a combined 55 percent. Domestic public debt (including central government and the central bank) was 8.9 percent of GDP at the end of 2010, of which nearly half (4.3 percent of GDP) were short-term maturities (IDA and IMF, 2011).

Nominal external public and publicly guaranteed debt amounted to 27.4 percent of GDP in 2009. About 90 percent of Burundi's outstanding nominal external public and publicly guaranteed debt was owed to multilateral creditors, with bilateral creditors accounting for the remainder. At about 21 percent of GDP, domestic debt accounted for about 43 percent of total public debt in 2009, compared with 13 percent in 2007. The main reason for the increasing importance of domestic debt was the cancellation of external public debt as a result of HIPC initiative and MDRI debt relief. Most domestic debt is owed to the central bank and has been used to finance government operations (IDA and IMF, 2010).

Once a country borrows, it has to pay the loan amount plus interest and associated cost (Debt servicing). This will therefore imply that the government uses resources which could be used to meet its expenditures to pay the debt. Debt service has crowded out funding for social and capital expenditures in these countries. After debt servicing and wage bill, there is little room left for core functions of the government, education, health, basic infrastructure, and other essential services, to create an enabling environment for the private sector. For example, according to WB (1993), in 1989 Kenya's debt service was more than a third of its export earnings, while in Tanzania debt payments was 86 percent of export earnings in 1987 (Kiringai, 2002).

2. Literature on External Debt and Growth

2.1 Theoretical Literature

According to the debt overhang hypothesis, if debt will exceed the country's repayment ability with some probability in the future, expected debt service is likely to be an increasing function of the country's output level. Thus some of the returns from investing in the domestic economy are effectively 'taxed' away by existing foreign creditors and investment by domestic and new foreign investors is discouraged (Claessens *et al.* 1996).

Were (2001) argues that the scope of debt overhang is much wider in that the effects of debt do not only affect investment in physical capital but any activity that involves incurring costs up-front for the sake of increased output in the future. Such activities include investment in human capital (in terms of education and health) and in technology acquisition whose effects on growth may be even stronger over time.

Debt obligations affect economic growth through "crowding out" effect on investments. If a greater proportion of foreign capital is used to service external debt, very little will be available for investment and growth. Debt-servicing cost of public debt can crowd out public investment expenditure, by reducing total investment directly and complementary private expenditures indirectly (Karagol, 2002).

According to Agénor and Montiel (1996), as the size of the public debt increases, there is growing uncertainty about actions and policies that the government will resort to in order to meet its debt servicing obligations, with adverse effects on investment. In particular, as the stock of public sector debt increases, there may be expectations that the government's debt service obligations will be financed by distortionary measures such as inflation tax.

Debt and lack of growth are clearly interrelated. The large debt stock and crushing debt service burden have now introduced a new "vicious cycle" to the analysis of the development problem of Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. In many SSA countries, debt servicing in the face of inadequate foreign exchange earnings leads to severe import strangulation. Import strangulation holds back export growth, thus perpetuating import shortages. The debt overhang and other uncertainties created by the debt situation further depress investment. Falling investment combined with shortages of essential imports results in declining real output. Declining output and escalating current account deficits lead to increasing debt and rising debt service obligations (Iyoha, 2000).

2.2 Empirical Literature

Were (2001) finds that current debt flows stimulate investment while past debt accumulation discourages investment in Kenya. This confirms the existence of debt overhang problem in Kenya. It has also been found that 'crowding out' of current investment as a result of servicing relatively large amounts of external debt so debt servicing does not appear to affect growth adversely but has some crowding out effects on private investments. Pattillo *et al.* (2004), however, are unable to find evidence of a significant crowding out effect while Chowdhury (2004) and Clements *et al.* (2003) find both debt burden and debt service obligations have reduced the investment and economic performance.

According to a study by Iyoha (2000), he opines that a 75 percent debt stock reduction would have raised the investment - GDP ratio by 8.6 percent and increased GDP by 7.8 percent and the debt/GNP ratio would have fallen by 65 percent. No doubt, the debt reduction is expected to promote growth. Deshpande (1997) also comes to the conclusion that relationship between external debt and investment is negative.

Mbanga and Sikod (2001) found that there exist a debt overhang and crowding-out effects on private and public investments respectively in Cameroon. However, Cohen (1993) investigates the correlation between developing countries (LDCs) debt and investment in the 1980s and established that the level of stock of debt does not appear to have much power to explain the slowdown in investment in developing countries during

the 1980s. It is the actual flows of net transfers that matter. He found that the actual service of debt 'crowded out' investment.

The literature discussed above shows mixed results on the relationship between public debt and investment. It can be broadly concluded that divergent opinions exist on the relationship between debt and the key determinants of economic growth such as investment.

3. Methodology

The following equation was estimated to establish the effect of public debt on public investment:

$$PI_{i,t} = \beta X_{i,t} + \gamma D_{i,t} + \mu_i + v_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3.1)$$

where: PI - is Public Investment.

$X_{i,t}$ - represent the set of explanatory variables.

$D_{i,t}$ - is the debt variable (external and aggregate public debts).

μ_i - unobserved country-specific effects.

v_t - unobserved time-specific effects.

$\varepsilon_{i,t}$ - is the error term.

and the subscripts i and t represent country and time period respectively.

$Y_{i,t}$ represent dependent variable, that is public investment. The $X_{i,t}$ are different explanatory variables that were used. The variables are the openness, government size, debt service ratio and terms of trade growth.

4. Data

4.1 Variables, Measurement and Sources of Data

PI-Public Investments: Investment refers to the addition of capital stock in an economy. Theoretically, Investment is the key to economic growth, if investment rises in an economy, aggregate demand also rise and therefore economic growth. Jorgenson (2003) obtained that investment in tangible assets is the most important source of economic growth in the Group of Seven (G7) nations. This variable is measured as a ratio of GDP. Data source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

ED-External Debt: External debt refers to credit owed to foreign lenders. The service of external debt may discourage public investment in an economy hence growth. Clements *et al.* (2005) argue that larger debt service can inhibit growth by squeezing public resources available for investment. This variable is expressed as a ratio of GDP. Data Source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

PD - Public Debt: Public debt refers to money or credit owed by any level of government. At low levels, debt is good. It is a source of economic growth and stability if well managed. But at high levels, private and public debts are bad, increasing volatility and retarding growth. (Cecchetti *et al.*, 2011). This variable is measured as the ratio of external debt plus internal debt to GDP. Data Source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

DS-Debt Service: The cash that is required for a particular time period to cover the repayment of interest and principal on debt. Larger debt service crowds out funding for social and capital expenditures in countries with large debt burdens. This variable is measured as a ratio of export earnings. Data Source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

GVTE - Government Expenditure: Government expenditure refers to general government final consumption expenditure as a share of GDP. Larger government provide public goods, further increases in government expenditure can increase the disposable incomes of the citizens which encourages growth. Data Source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

OPNS – Openness: Openness refers to the sum of exports and imports of goods and services as a share of GDP. According to World Bank (1993), significant growth rates are often associated with countries embracing the ongoing globalisation and increasing openness to the international exchange of goods and services as well as ideas and technologies. This variable is measured as the ratio of imports (M) plus exports (X) to GDP $[(M + X) / GDP]$. Data Source: Penn World Tables (7.1).

TOT - Terms of Trade: Terms of trade refers to the price of a country's exports (P_X) relative to the price of its imports (P_M), ($TOT = P_X / P_M$). Where P_X is a price index for all export goods due to the fact that countries export more than one good, P_M is a price index for all import goods. Mendoza (1997) proposes a stochastic growth model whereby terms of trade uncertainty can adversely affect savings and growth. Data Source: WDI (2011) Data Base.

5. Empirical Analysis and Presentation of Results

5.1 Panel Unit Root Tests

Before conducting any econometric study, the data should be checked whether it is stationary or not. According to Granger and Newbold (1974), if we run a regression in the level form while the variables in the model are non-stationary, it may lead to unauthentic results, so it's important that the series of data be stationary. Due to this econometric problem, this study employed the Levin-Lin-Chu (LLC) method to check the stationarity of the variables. Levin- Lin-Chu test is based on the following hypotheses:

H_0 : Each time series contains a unit root.

H_1 : Each time series is stationary.

The results of the panel unit root tests for the variables are summarized and presented in Table 1.

Table 1: LLC Tests for Stationarity/Unit root tests for all variables (variables in levels)

Variable	LLC (Level)	LLC (First Difference)	LLC (P-Value) Level	Order of Integration
PI	t: -1.2337	-8.7587	0.7462	I(1)
	t*: -1.720	-5.3288		
ED	t: -1.3853	-1.3845	0.6102	I(1)
	t*: -1.3642	-1.3629		
PD	t: -2.5997	-7.5289	0.3156	I(1)
	t*:-0.4801	-4.0902		
OPNS	t: -1.4523	-5.1897	0.5978	I(1)
	t*: -1.3151	-3.2571		
GVTE	t: -1.8619	-4.1003	0.1783	I(1)
	t*: -1.7187	-2.9438		
TOT	t: -1.1113	-4.2445	0.8646	I(1)
	t*:-1.0207	-2.9929		
DS	t: -1.5662	-4.8588	0.5261	I(1)
	t*:-1.3780	-3.1609		

Critical Values: -2.460 (1%); -2.180 (5%); -2.040 (10%).

From the results in Table 1, all the variables are integrated of order one (I (1)) and were found to be stationary after differencing them once.

5.2 Cointegration Tests

After obtaining the order of integration of the variables, the next step was to establish whether the non-stationary variables are cointegrated. Usually, when variables are differenced to attain stationarity, the long-run properties are lost. Cointegration means that there is a long-run relationship between two or more non-stationary variables. The study had all the variables non-stationary (I (1)). Therefore, cointegration test was carried out using the Engle-Granger two-step procedure. This was carried out by generating residuals from the long-run equations of the non-stationary variables and LLC unit root test was carried out which established that the residuals were stationary at 5 percent level of significance. This confirmed the existence of cointegration and therefore an Error Correction Model was adopted.

5.3 The Error Correction Model (ECM)

Since all the variables in the model were I (1), cointegration test was carried out using the Engle-Granger two-step procedure and it was established that there was evidence of cointegration. Consequently, an error correction model was used. Therefore, equation 3.1 was rewritten to include the error correction term as follows:

$$DPI_{i,t} = \beta X_{i,t} + \gamma D_{i,t} + \tau ECT_{i,t-1} + \mu_i + v_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \tag{5.1}$$

Where *ECT*- is the error correction term.

The error correction model provides a framework for testing asymmetric and non-linear adjustment to long-run equilibrium. The short-run model shows how the adjustment mechanism works to revert to equilibrium condition when it is disturbed by exogenous shocks which lead to deviations from the long-run equilibrium. The error correction term captures the long-run relationship and tells us the speed with which the model returns to equilibrium following an exogenous shock. It should be negatively signed, indicating a move back towards equilibrium, a positive sign indicates movement away from equilibrium. The coefficient should lie between 0 and 1, 0 suggesting no adjustment one time period later while 1 indicates full adjustment. In the EAC, some of the shocks arise as a result of political instabilities, for example, civil wars in Uganda in 1980s, Rwanda genocide in 1994 and post-election violence in Kenya in 1992 and 2008.

5.4 Hausman Test

In order to decide whether to use random or fixed effects model, Hausman (1978) proposed a test for such a situation. Therefore, Hausman test is carried out and the null hypothesis is that the preferred model is random effects vs. the alternative fixed effects. It basically tests whether the errors are correlated with the regressors, the null hypothesis is that they are not. Hausman test looks at the difference in the coefficient estimates using fixed effects and random effects estimators. Hausman test was carried out and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Hausman Test Results

$\chi^2 (5)$	=	13.42
Prob > χ^2	=	0.0375

Test: H₀: difference in coefficients not systematic

From the Hausman test results in Table 2, the p-value is 0.0375, less than 0.05. This shows that the value is significant and therefore fixed effects model is applicable in regression. The fixed effects model was therefore chosen based on Hausman test carried out.

5.5 Test for Cross-Sectional Dependence

Cross-sectional dependence is the interaction between cross-sectional units. Cross-sectional dependence leads to efficiency loss for least squares and invalidates conventional t -tests and F -tests which use standard variance-covariance estimators. The study employed the Breush-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test of independence. The null hypothesis is that the residuals across entities are not correlated. The test results for cross-sectional dependence are presented Table 3.

5.6 Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity is a situation where the error terms do not have constant variance. It can be caused by measurement errors and if there are subpopulation differences or other interaction effects. Heteroscedasticity does not lead to biased parameter estimates, however, the standard errors are biased if heteroscedasticity is present. This in turn leads to bias in test statistics and confidence intervals. The test results for heteroscedasticity are presented Table 3.

5.7 Test for Serial Correlation

Serial correlation occurs when the error terms from different time periods (or cross-section observations) are correlated. According to Drukker (2003), serial correlation in linear panel-data models biases the standard errors and causes the results to be less efficient, therefore, serial correlation should be identified in the idiosyncratic error term in a panel data model. A new test by Wooldridge (2002) is very attractive because it requires relatively few assumptions and is easy to implement. A test for serial correlation was conducted and the results presented Table 3.

5.8 Public Debt and Public Investments in EAC

This study aims at finding out the channels through which public debt may manifest itself on economic growth rate. The study therefore investigates how external and public debts impact on the EAC's public investment by regressing equation 5.1. This is carried out using two different models and the results are presented in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Results of Public Investments and External Debt Regression

Dependent Variable: DPI		Method: Fixed Effects Regression		
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
CONSTANT	11.3022	5.5071	2.05	0.109
DED	-0.2350	0.098	-2.40	0.037
DS	-0.1005	0.0451	-2.23	0.045
DGVTE	0.3380	0.1055	3.20	0.023
DOPNS	0.2483	0.119	2.09	0.052
DTOT	-0.0032	0.0377	-0.09	0.936
ECT _{t-1}	-0.2538	0.0687	-3.69	0.021
Adj. R ² = 0.6057		Durbin Watson = 1.9245		
F (8, 196) = 37.6364		P-value (F) = 0.0000		
Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence	χ^2 (10) = 10.265		0.1452	
Heteroscedasticity		χ^2 (5) = 52.014		0.1103
Wooldridge test for Panel Data		F (1, 4) = 5.283		0.2473

The results obtained indicate that the coefficient of external debt is negative and statistically significant at 5 percent level. This means that on average, if the external debt levels increase by 1 unit, public investments decline by 0.235 units. Therefore, a country that experiences huge external debt burden is likely to have low levels of public investments. This is true for the case of the EAC member countries where investments in physical infrastructure is very poor by the governments due external debt servicing. The governments have to meet the local currency requirements for debt service which makes them to borrow from the banks and the result is crowding out of private investors. Further, external debt creates a lot of uncertainties in the economy, for example, taxes may be raised to meet the debt obligations and this discourages investors from investing locally. The results conform to the findings by Were (2001) and Iyoha (2000) who established that debt servicing has some crowding out effects on investments.

The results show that a rise in the level of debt service negatively affects public investment. This is due to the fact that larger external debt-service repayments can hinder public investments by draining the public resources which could be used for development of infrastructure and human capital. Also external debt has

strings attached and interest payments on the debt can reduce public savings by widening a country's budget deficit. This confirms the 'crowding-out' effect of debt service on public investment.

There is a positive relationship between public investments and government expenditure which is statistically significant at 5 percent level. Therefore, a unit rise in government expenditure leads to 0.3380 units increase in public investments. In the EAC, most of the public sector investments such as provision of physical infrastructure, health and education are normally carried out by the governments.

The results also indicate that there is a positive influence of openness and public investment. Openness can encourage domestic production which may increase government investments in certain key industries in the economy thereby increasing the capital stock. The relationship between public investment and terms of trade is negative and but not statistically significant for the model.

The error correction term was lagged (ECT_{t-1}) and included in the model to capture the long-run dynamics between the cointegrating series. It has the correct sign (negative) and is statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance. It proves of the existence of long term relationship among the variables under study. The coefficient indicates a speed of adjustment of 25.4 percent from actual growth in the previous year to equilibrium rate of public investments. The speed of adjustment is relatively low, implying that the deviations are not corrected within a year and in most situations the economies might be operating in disequilibrium.

The variations in public investments are explained up to 60.57 percent by the variables in the model, as shown by the Adj. R^2 . The value of Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.9245, which is very close to 2 and therefore the model does not suffer from serial correlation. The F value also shows that the parameters in the model are jointly significant at 1 percent level.

In Table 3, the results show that there is no cross-sectional dependence of the cross-sectional units since the p-value is greater than 0.05. The results show the absence of heteroscedasticity as shown by the p-value of the test (0.1103). The results further confirm the absence of serial correlation since the p-value of Wooldridge test is 0.2473, which is greater than 0.05.

Table 4: Results of Public Investments and Public Debt Regression

Dependent Variable: DPI

Method: Fixed Effects Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value
CONSTANT	10.638	5.29	2.01	0.104
DPD	-0.1460	0.044	-3.32	0.026

DS	-0.2102	0.0968	-2.17	0.031
DGVTE	0.3772	0.0841	4.49	0.011
DOPNS	0.2590	0.076	3.41	0.023
DTOT	-0.0255	0.0075	-3.40	0.024
ECT _{t-1}	-0.2933	0.0525	-5.59	0.005
Adj. R ² = 0.7544		Durbin Watson = 1.8589		
F (9, 115) = 48.61		P-value (F) = 0.0000		
Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence	χ^2 (10) = 8.341			0.2587
Heteroscedasticity				
	χ^2 (5) = 39.85			0.1018
Wooldridge test for Panel Data				0.2136
	F (1, 4) = 5.984			

The regression results in Table 4 indicate that public debt negatively and significantly affects public investments, as shown by the negative coefficient of public debt. The results show that on average, if public debt burden increases by 1 unit, public investments decrease by 0.146 units and is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The trend of public debt in EAC shows that the public debt burden in 1980s and 1990s was very high with countries such as Rwanda and Burundi having debt levels of over 90 percent of the GDP in some instances. Servicing such a huge debt burden consumes a large portion of government resources leaving very little for development projects and consequently decreasing economic growth. The results are consistent to the findings by Iyoha (1999) and Krugman (1988).

The results further confirm that debt servicing crowds-out public investment in EAC. These findings concur with those of Checherita and Rother (2010), Karagol (2002) and Chowdhury (2004) who established that debt servicing cost on public debt can crowd-out public investment expenditure by reducing total investment directly and complementary private expenditures indirectly thereby impeding economic performance. In contrast to these findings, Patillo *et al.* (2004) are unable to find evidence of significant crowding out effect of debt on investments.

The regression results show that the coefficient of government expenditure is positive and significant at 5 percent level of significance. This implies that a unit increase in government expenditure leads to 0.3772 units increase in public investments. This is because government expenditure constitutes capital expenditure which increases the level of public investments. This means that as government expenditure rises, infrastructure

networks such as roads, transport networks, water, health facilities, education and public investments rise in the EAC.

Openness and public investment have a positive relationship which is statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance. Trade liberalization leads to industrialization which promotes the growth of public investments. The EAC countries are open economies meaning that they are likely to have increased public investments as consequence of this. From the results, adverse terms of trade lead to a decline public investments in EAC. The coefficient of terms of trade is negative and significant at 5 percent level. When a country experiences unfavorable terms of trade, gains from trade also decline implying that small earnings from trade cannot then be used to increase the levels of domestic investments. The region faces adverse terms of trade caused by the nature of the commodities they specialize in. Terms of trade volatility tends to induce volatility in consumer spending, investment, inflation and economic growth thereby making macroeconomic policies difficult to implement. The EAC countries are developing and usually face sharp swings in export prices which contribute to increased volatility in public sector spending. The error correction term was lagged one period (ECT_{t-1}) and included in the model to capture the long-run dynamics between the cointegrating series. It has the correct sign (negative) and is statistically significant at 1 percent level. It proves of the existence of long term relationship among the variables under study. The coefficient indicates a speed of adjustment of 29.33 percent from actual growth in the previous year to equilibrium rate of public investments.

The Adj. R^2 value is 0.7544, suggesting that the model explains approximately 75.44 percent of the variations in PI. For this model, the value of Durbin-Watson is 1.8589, approximately equal to 2, indicating absence of autocorrelation. The F value in this model is $F(8, 116) = 48.61$, with a p-value (F) = 0.0000 implying that all the regression parameters are non-zero and that the regression equation has some validity in fitting the data.

From the cross-sectional test dependence results in Table 4, the p-value is greater than 0.05, therefore insignificant. It tells us that there is no cross-sectional dependence of the cross-sectional units. The p-value of heteroscedasticity results is greater than 0.05 which reveals no heteroscedasticity. Therefore the null hypothesis for homoscedasticity is accepted. From the results of autocorrelation in Table 4, the p-value is greater than 0.05, therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the data does not have serial correlation.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

The main focus of this study was to establish the effect of public debt on public investment of the EAC member countries. This was aimed at examining whether public investment is one of the channels through which debt manifest itself on growth. Regression results of external debt, public and public investment

revealed that external debt and public debt expansion have a negative effect on public investment of the EAC member countries. If properly utilised, external debt can help the developing countries like EAC to meet their development goals, but this has not been the case.

From the Error Correction Models, the error correction terms included in the two models were lagged (ECT_{t-1}) and included in the models to capture the long-run dynamics between the cointegrating series. They have the correct sign (negative) and also significant which confirms the existence of long term relationship among the variables under study. The results show that openness promotes public investment in EAC countries while terms of trade negatively affects public investment in the region. The EAC countries should improve their terms of trade by processing their exports, improvement in terms of trade increases domestic real income which raises the level of public investments and therefore growth.

As indicated by Karagol (2002), debt obligations affect economic growth through “crowding out” effect on investments. If a greater proportion of foreign capital is used to service external debt, very little will be available for investment and growth. Debt-servicing cost of public debt can crowd out public investment expenditure, by reducing total investment directly and complementary private expenditures indirectly.

The two public investment models also showed that there was some crowding-out of public investment as a result of servicing relatively large amounts of external debt and public debt. The findings suggest that for the each country in EAC, reducing public debt levels would contribute to growth by reducing the “crowding out” effect that debt has on investments. This is because reducing the stock of debt will lead to lower debt service obligations which are likely to induce governments to increase their spending on public investment.

Debt servicing is very costly if not issued on concessional terms and this reduces the meagre public resources which could have been used to promote investments in certain key sectors of the economy such as roads, energy, education, health and information and communications technology (ICT) and also investment in machinery and equipment. The result of low public investments is a decline in capital formation and hence economic growth.

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